

Beyond Traditional Learning: Digital Escape Rooms as an Engaging Tool for Mastering Integral Calculus

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Abstract

The integration of digital escape rooms (ER) into mathematics education has garnered increasing attention as a strategy to enhance student engagement and promote active learning (Borrego et al., 2017; Jensen et al., 2022). In today's higher education landscape, students have access to a diverse range of learning methodologies, including blended learning, adaptive learning technologies, and game-based instructional approaches that cater to different learning styles and preferences (Sailer et al., 2017).

This study examines the impact of the MATH-DIGGER digital escape room, ER1, on students' learning experiences in the context of integral calculus. Participants completed pre- and post-questionnaires to assess their expectations regarding escape rooms as a learning tool, their preferred learning styles, their confidence in solving mathematical problems, and their perceived difficulties both in learning mathematics and engaging with the ER 3D-environment. The collected data underwent statistical analysis to identify trends and correlations that provide insights into the effectiveness of this approach. Additionally, the structure and mechanics of the MATH-DIGGER ER1 are briefly described to contextualise its role in the learning experience (Babo et al., 2023; Pinto et al., 2024; Rasteiro et al., 2024).

Preliminary results indicate that students generally held positive expectations about learning through ER and demonstrated higher engagement compared to traditional instructional methods. However, the analysis also revealed variations in students' confidence levels and their ability to navigate mathematical challenges within the ER, highlighting key areas for pedagogical improvement. Furthermore, specific learning difficulties in integral calculus were observed, suggesting potential refinements in the design of future digital ER to better support conceptual understanding and problem-solving skills.

This study contributes to the growing body of research on gamified learning and mathematics education, demonstrating the potential of ER to create a more interactive and immersive learning experience. The findings offer valuable insights into the design and implementation of game-based learning environments in higher education mathematics curricula.

Keywords: Digital Escape Rooms, Mathematics Education, Integral Calculus, Gamified Learning, Student Engagement, Active Learning

Introduction

The design and evaluation of educational escape rooms (ERs) have attracted growing interest as innovative approaches to promoting learning through gamification and active engagement (Piñero Charlo, J. C., 2020; Queiruga-Dios, A. et.al., 2020). A central element in these experiences is the Game User Experience (GUX), which encompasses participants' interactions with the game, their perceptions, and the value they derive from

it. Gaining insight into the core dimensions of GUX enables educators and developers to assess the effectiveness of escape rooms not only as engaging learning environments but also as instruments for the development of knowledge and transversal skills (Veldkamp, Alice, 2020).

In educational escape rooms (ERs), thoughtfully developed storylines significantly contribute to the pedagogical relevance of gameplay. By situating tasks within authentic, real-life contexts, these narratives strengthen the alignment between in-game challenges and intended learning outcomes, thereby enhancing both immersion and educational value. In the MATH-DIGGER experience "ER1 – Sustainable Environment on University Facilities" (Babo et al., 2023; Pinto et al., 2024; Rasteiro et al., 2024), the storyline is centred on the reconstruction of a university campus following a severe environmental disaster. Confronted with resource scarcity and strict governmental sustainability mandates, participants engage in missions related to pivotal domains: urban development, energy, environmental stewardship, and demographic change. With conventional energy sources disrupted, players (students) resort to installing solar panels to reactivate university functions, underscoring the necessity of resilience and eco-conscious innovation. The escape room seamlessly combines problem-solving tasks with an inquiry-based pedagogical approach, framed by a narrative of ecological recovery. Evaluating the Game User Experience (GUX) across multiple dimensions offers critical insights into the effectiveness of educational escape rooms. By closely examining student interactions within these environments, educators and designers can both highlight successful elements and detect areas needing refinement. This structured analysis ensures that escape rooms serve not only as captivating experiences but also as meaningful educational tools. A concrete example of this approach is found in MATH-DIGGER Escape Room 1, developed within the framework of the Erasmus+ MATH-DIGGER project. Tailored for first-year engineering students, this escape room weaves together topics of sustainability and energy efficiency with core mathematical content from Calculus I. Grounded in inquiry-based learning (IBL) methodology, the game challenges participants with activities such as interpolation and integral calculus, fostering active learning in a gamified setting.

The paper is organised as follows: the present section provides a brief introduction to the use of escape rooms in educational contexts and highlights the importance of analysing the game user experience to enhance their educational impact. The methodology section describes the participants involved in the study and outlines the data collection procedures. This is followed by the results section, which presents the data analysis and discussion. Finally, the paper concludes with a section summarising the main findings and offering insights for future research.

Methodology

The data collection process was conducted among first-year engineering students of Mathematical Analysis from the graduation in Electrical and Computer Engineering, which is one of the engineering graduation courses of the Coimbra Engineering Institute in the Polytechnic University of Coimbra. Students were invited to participate in a pilot test of the ER1 that was implemented under the MATH-DIGGER Erasmus+ project. Two

questionnaires, a pre- and a post-questionnaire, were completed by the students who participated in this pilot study. A total of 66 students responded to the pre-questionnaire, while 33 students completed the post-questionnaire. Students that do not answer the post-questionnaire were students who dropped the pilot test or did not even start it. To ensure the reliability and validity of the data collected, both the pre- and post-questionnaires were administered through Google Forms and included clear instructions, while emphasising the voluntary and anonymous nature of student participation. Participation in the ER1 activity was incorporated into the course grade for Mathematical Analysis, worth 4 points out of 20 (20% of the final grade). The incorporation was intended to encourage student participation and to acknowledge the pedagogical value of the escape room activity. The pre-questionnaire was completed before the activity to collect baseline information on students' expectations and prior knowledge, whereas the post-questionnaire was administered at the end of the pilot study, allowing participants to immediately reflect on their experience. This dual-survey design enabled the timely and systematic collection of data, offering valuable insights into students' perceptions of ER1 as both a gamified experience and an educational tool. The responses provide a comprehensive basis for evaluating the escape room's effectiveness in conveying key calculus concepts within the context of sustainability.

Results

The data collected was analysed using IBM SPSS version 29 (IBM Corp., 2022). To evaluate the potential impact of the educational escape room on students' perceptions and experiences, a paired samples t-test was conducted comparing responses from the pre- and post-questionnaires. The results, as may be observed in Table 1,

Table 1. Paired Samples t-test

		Paired Differences					Significance			
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	df	One-Sided p	Two-Sided p
					Lower	Upper				
Pair 1	Mathematic Interest - Mathematic Interest	.167	.913	.167	-.174	.508	1.000	29	.163	.326
Pair 2	Mathematic Knowledge - Mathematic Knowledge	-.167	.950	.173	-.521	.188	-.961	29	.172	.344
Pair 3	Trust Level in Solving Math Problems - Trust Level in Solving Math Problems	-.167	.791	.145	-.462	.129	-1.153	29	.129	.258
Pair 4	Games Usage in Learning Environment - Games Usage in Learning Environment	-.167	.950	.173	-.521	.188	-.961	29	.172	.344
Pair 5	How Comfortable Using TIC in Learning Activities - How Comfortable Using TIC in Learning Activities	-.033	.556	.102	-.241	.174	-.328	29	.373	.745
Pair 6	ER Familiarity as a Learning Tool - ER Familiarity as a Learning Tool	-.167	.461	.084	-.339	.006	-1.980	29	.029	.057
Pair 7	ER Efficiency in Math Learning - ER Efficiency in Math Learning	.133	1.502	.274	-.428	.694	.486	29	.315	.631

showed no statistically significant differences across the seven measured dimensions, including mathematical interest, self-perceived knowledge, trust in solving mathematical problems, and perceptions of games and technologies in learning.

Although none of the comparisons reached statistical significance at the 5% level, the item related to ER familiarity as a learning tool (Pair 6) approached significance ($p = 0.057$). This suggests a potential trend toward increased familiarity, although the effect was not strong enough to be conclusive. In contrast, other items such as perceived mathematical knowledge, trust in solving problems, and perceptions of game use in education (Pairs 2 - 4) showed similar mean differences but with wider confidence intervals and higher p-values, indicating weaker and more uncertain effects. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that all confidence intervals lie predominantly within the negative range, which may suggest a tendency toward improvement following the activity, despite the lack of statistical significance.

These findings suggest that while the activity was well-received, it did not produce measurable changes in the surveyed constructs after a single intervention.

Besides the pre- and post- questionnaires, a questionnaire, based on the GUESS-18 (Keebler, J. R., 2020), aimed to capture various dimensions of the escape room experience, including usability/playability, narrative, play engrossment, enjoyment, creative freedom, audio aesthetics, personal gratification, social connectivity, and visual aesthetics. Responses were collected via a Google Forms survey, which facilitated efficient distribution, user-friendly interaction, and secure data collection. A total of 49 valid responses were collected from the same set of students who answered the pre- and

post-questionnaires, with no missing data across the variables analysed. The sample was composed primarily of male students (92% male), with a mean age of 19.80 years ($SD = 1.92$), aligning with the expected demographic profile of first-year students in engineering programmes. All participants were enrolled in the same Higher Education Institution (IPC/ISEC) and academic level, ensuring a controlled educational context for the escape room activity.

Regarding prior experience with Games and Escape Rooms, participants reported moderate familiarity with digital games in general, with a mean score of 4.69 ($SD = 1.75$) for the item assessing frequency of playing games and 4.37 ($SD = 1.83$) for perceived usefulness of games in learning environments. These values indicate that students are generally open to game-based learning. Familiarity with escape rooms as educational tools was lower, with a mean of 3.69 ($SD = 1.72$), suggesting that while the majority had some awareness, direct experience was not widespread. This finding supports the exploratory and potentially novel nature of the activity for many participants.

Student responses to GUX-related items revealed an overall positive perception of the educational escape room design. Usability aspects such as interface ($M = 4.24$, $SD = 1.65$) and controls ($M = 4.65$, $SD = 1.81$) were rated favourably, suggesting that the technical design supported smooth interaction. Narrative elements were also appreciated, with story coherence ($M = 4.16$, $SD = 1.61$) and fantasy elements ($M = 4.12$, $SD = 1.67$) both receiving high scores. Emotional engagement was evident, with students reporting the game as fun ($M = 4.10$, $SD = 1.57$) and stimulating to creativity ($M = 4.18$, $SD = 1.81$) and imagination ($M = 3.82$, $SD = 1.70$). The item “feeling bored” yielded a lower mean of 3.88, confirming a generally engaging experience. Perceived immersion, although moderate, was present. Items such as “detachment from the real world” ($M = 3.57$, $SD = 1.77$) and “immersion in game events” ($M = 3.37$, $SD = 1.84$) reflected varying degrees of absorption in the storyline and gameplay.

Aesthetic and auditory components were well-received. Students positively evaluated the visual appeal ($M = 4.08$, $SD = 1.79$) and graphics ($M = 3.94$, $SD = 1.71$) of the escape room. The role of sound in the experience was also acknowledged, with sound effects ($M = 3.65$, $SD = 1.99$) and audio enhancement ($M = 4.00$, $SD = 2.00$) contributing positively to immersion and satisfaction. In terms of social engagement, results indicate moderate interaction, with students reporting social interaction with peers ($M = 3.55$, $SD = 1.75$) and enjoyment of playing with others ($M = 3.55$, $SD = 1.87$). While the activity was not designed as a multiplayer game per se, these results suggest that peer presence and collaboration were at least partially perceived as part of the learning experience.

Finally, students reported high levels of perceived competence and motivation. The items “focus on own performance” ($M = 4.61$, $SD = 1.54$) and “feeling able to do well” ($M = 5.35$, $SD = 1.64$) suggest a strong internal drive to succeed and a sense of efficacy during the activity. These findings indicate that the educational escape room supported not only engagement and enjoyment but also students’ confidence in their ability to complete learning tasks effectively. The distribution of responses for each GUX item can be observed in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Distribution of responses for GUX items (Excel graphic)

The descriptive and inferential analyses suggest that students perceived the escape room experience positively across multiple dimensions of Game User Experience (GUX), particularly regarding usability, narrative coherence, and perceived learning support. While variability existed across some items, especially those related to emotional immersion and social interaction, the general pattern indicates consistent engagement with the activity. The high self-assessed motivation and confidence reported by participants further reinforce the activity’s alignment with learner needs and preferences. In addition to the data collected from the students, an individual assessment of their performance in ER1 was also carried out. This evaluation was based on the criteria presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Evaluation Criteria for ER1

Evaluation Criteria	Description	Weight # (%)
Correct answers.	Proportion of correct answers in mathematical challenges.	1.20 (30%)
Number of attempts made.	Number of times the student attempted to complete challenges, assessing persistence.	0.40 (10%)
Execution time and progression.	Time required to complete levels, considering improvement between attempts.	0.60 (15%)
Collected objects/in-game interaction.	The quantity of educational objects collected reflects attention and exploration of the environment.	0.40 (10%)
Evolution throughout the game.	Comparison between the beginning and end of the game, evaluating progress and learning.	0.60 (15%)
Levels completed successfully.	Number and complexity of levels completed in the game.	0.40 (10%)
Autonomy and efficiency in problem solving.	Ability to solve challenges with few errors and without external help.	0.40 (10%)

The results, on a scale of 0 to 4 points, reveal an average performance of 2.76, with a median of 2.7, demonstrating an overall positive performance. The dispersion of results, with a standard deviation of approximately 0.61, shows moderate heterogeneity in the group. Of the 33 students who responded to the post-questionnaire, 31 completed at least one part of the MATH-DIGGER digital escape room, ER1, and obtained a valid performance score. The remaining two students dropped out after failing to progress beyond the first level, chose not to participate further, and obtained no points. Figure 2 shows the grade distribution obtained by students.

Figure 2. Distribution of student grades (scores) in ER1 across 4 levels. (Excel graphic)

Conclusions

This study aimed to evaluate the educational value of a digital escape room designed to support first-year engineering students in learning key concepts of Mathematical Analysis, within the context of sustainability. Two main data sources were considered: a pre- and post-questionnaire completed by participants, and a detailed analysis of their perceptions of the Game User Experience (GUX) during the activity. The results of the pre- and post-questionnaire analysis revealed no statistically significant differences across the measured dimensions, including students' interest in mathematics, perceived knowledge, confidence in solving mathematical problems, and familiarity with digital learning tools. Nonetheless, one variable – familiarity with escape rooms as a learning tool – approached significance ($p = 0.057$), suggesting a trend toward increased awareness and potential appreciation for this methodology. While this single exposure may not have substantially shifted core attitudes, it introduces a novel pedagogical tool within a traditional academic context. In contrast, the GUX analysis provided a more nuanced view of the learning experience. Students reported high levels of satisfaction with the escape room's usability, narrative quality, and integration of mathematical content. The activity was generally perceived as engaging, enjoyable, and conducive to learning, with strong scores in areas related to interface design and confidence in task performance. While some variability was observed in dimensions such as emotional immersion and social interaction, the overall pattern indicated that students found value in this gamified learning experience.

The assessment of student performance in ER1 revealed that most students demonstrated good adaptation to the game dynamics and reasonable mastery of the program content used in the escape room. The results suggest that ER1 was effective in consolidating mathematical concepts, promoting logical reasoning and problem solving in a playful way. In addition to the overall results obtained, it is worth highlighting the approach used to evaluate student participation in the MATH-DIGGER digital escape room developed.

This assessment was carried out according to a series of criteria, which were defined to measure not only cognitive capacity (skills such as attention, memory, reasoning, critical thinking and decision-making), but also students' involvement, improvement and problem-solving ability. The criteria defined were hits, attempts made, execution time and progression, number of objects picked up during the escape room, evolution throughout the game, levels successfully reached, and autonomy demonstrated in overcoming obstacles. All these parameters became part of the grade given to the student on a scale between 0 and 4 points, previously weighed so that the assessment was balanced and pedagogical. This allowed us to assess not only the mastery of mathematical content but also how students engaged in recreational and educational activities. Statistical analysis indicated that there is a positive correlation between game performance and knowledge consolidation, reinforcing the usefulness of innovative learning environments such as gamification for student engagement and concrete content learning.

Together, these findings suggest that while a single intervention may not be sufficient to produce measurable shifts in student attitudes or self-perceptions, the quality of the experience itself, as captured through GUX dimensions, plays a critical role in shaping student engagement and motivation. Educational escape rooms, when carefully designed and contextually aligned with curricular goals, can be used as powerful tools for supporting active learning, particularly in mathematically intensive courses. Future implementations might explore repeated or scaffolded use of such activities to foster deeper changes in students' perceptions and learning behaviours.

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